

Application of GIS in ground water quality mapping for Varanasi city

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Abstract : Ground water remains the drinking water source for a significant portion of population in India. In present study, a detailed program of ground water sampling and analyses have been done from 25 tube wells and 18 open wells of Varansi, UP (India). Chemical characteristics included nitrate, fluoride pH, dissolved oxygen (DO), BOD₅, electrical conductivity (EC), total dissolved solid (TDS), sulfate; chloride and alkalinity. The open wells and tube wells were evaluated for their suitability as a source for drinking purpose. The results indicate that the tube well waters in the area are generally safe for drinking, although alkalinity in many samples is beyond desirable limits for the purpose. TDS is also found high at many places. Water samples from open wells at two places are found to have nitrate concentrations beyond permissible limits. Around 88% of samples are found to have fluoride concentrations less than 1.0 mg/L. Geographical Information System (GIS) based water quality maps and contours of water quality parameters for Varanasi city have been prepared.

Keywords : Ground water quality, Varanasi city, GIS, TDS, nitrate, fluoride.

Introduction

Ground water is a vital component of our life support system on the earth. The ground water resources are being utilized for drinking, irrigation and industrial purposes. Due to the rapid growth of urbanization and industrialization, there is an increasing pressure on land, water and environment. Concentration of human population in urban areas has resulted in increase of buildings, roads, vehicles, factories, urban sewage and storm drains, smoke and dust, and garbage hazards which leads to severe water and air pollution^{1,2}. Pollutants are being added to the ground water system through human activities and natural processes. From the user's point of view, the term "water quality" is defined as "those physical, chemical or biological characteristics of water by which the user evaluates the acceptability of water", e.g. drinking water should be pure, wholesome and potable³. Water quality has mainly degraded by anthropogenic contamination activities⁴. In the coming next two decades many countries of world continents such as Africa, Middle East and South

Asia may will face with serious threats of water shortage⁵. Therefore, in the near future perhaps a water scarce condition will be occurred especially in developing countries of the world⁶.

A vast majority of ground water quality problems are caused by contamination, over-exploitation, or combination of the two. Most ground water quality problems are difficult to detect and hard to resolve. The solutions are usually very expensive, time consuming and not always effective. Quality maintenance of drinking water is very important to avoid impacts of toxic contaminants on living creatures including human beings. Further developments of water treatment and analytical techniques are required for the conservation of water⁷. An alarming picture is beginning to emerge in many parts of our country. Ground water quality is slowly but surely declining everywhere. Essentially all activities carried out on land have the potential to contaminate the ground water, whether associated with urban, industrial or agricultural activities. Large scale, concentrated sources of pollution

such as industrial discharges, landfills and subsurface injection of chemicals and hazardous wastes, are an obvious source of ground water pollution. These concentrated sources can be easily detected and regulated but the more difficult problem is associated with diffuse sources of pollution like leaching of agrochemicals and animal wastes subsurface discharges from septic tanks and infiltration of polluted urban run-off and sewage. Diffuse sources can affect entire aquifers, which is difficult to control and treat. The only solution to diffuse sources of pollution is to integrate land use with water management. Once pollution has entered the sub-surface environment, it may remain concealed for many years, becoming dispersed over wide areas and rendering ground water supplies unsuitable for human uses. In the present study, water quality of Varanasi city has been studied for mapping and earmarking different areas of the city with respect to drinking purpose. The city's water needs are partly met from surface and partly from ground water sources. An attempt has been made to study the spatial variation of ground water quality based on the integrated analysis of physico-chemical parameters and use of Geographic Information System (GIS).

GIS Based ground water quality mapping :

GIS is an information system that is designed to work with data referenced by spatial or geographical coordinates. In other words GIS is both a database system with specific capabilities for spatially referenced data as well as a set of operations for working with the data⁸. In modern water resource development and hydrological study, GIS and Remote Sensing are playing a significant role. Using Remote Sensing for hydrological investigations has got many advantages; one of these is its tendency to generate information in spatial and temporal domain, which then goes to analysis, prediction and validation respectively. GIS technology is suitable alternative for providing an efficient management of large and complex data base⁹. Assessment of quality of ground water through spatial distribution mapping for various pollutants utilizing GIS technology and the resulted information on quality of water could be useful for policy makers to take remedial measures¹⁰⁻¹².

The various thematic maps can be generated using standard functionalities available in GIS software for over-

lay analysis. These thematic layers with suitable attribution and results derived from GIS analysis can be used to create input maps required to zone and classify the areas suitable for use¹³.

Generation of water quality maps :

Water quality maps for different parameter have been generated using spatial analyst extension in ArcGIS. Inverse Distance Weighted tool in Interpolate to raster method has been used for generation of water quality maps. Different colors are given based on the suitability of water for domestic purposes.

Results and discussion

Sampling for water quality analyses have been done from two types of sources (i.e. open wells and tube wells). The following tables given show the result of water quality analysis of open wells and tube wells samples collected in month of March, 2010.

Depth of open wells :

It is observed that in most part of the city the water table is in between 5–21 m. The north area of Varanasi city near its boundary Shivpur, Bhojubeer, Chiragaon, Kamauli, Paigambarpur, have water table 15 m below ground level (BGL). The people living in these areas may face problem of water crisis in month of summer because more extraction of ground water. Some middle area of the city like Alaipur, Beniabagh Gatgunj, Chetgunj and Chuakaghat may be at risk of water logging condition in monsoon periods. Tube wells are major sources of drinking water in Varanasi city. The observation indicates that all of the tube wells draw water from more than 100 m depth.

Dissolved oxygen :

Dissolved oxygen (D.O.) is generally taken as the measure of freshness of water. Both open well and tube well water samples were analyzed for their D.O. values. The D.O. of drinking water source without conventional treatment should not be less than 6 mg/L³. It is observed that D.O. concentration varies between 6.0–7.5 mg/L for all tube well samples, indicating them to be safe for drinking purpose. Open well water samples indicate much wider variation of D.O. level (2.0–7.5 mg/L). Around 33% of open well samples are found to have D.O. levels below 5 mg/L, which is considered not safe for drinking³. Most

Table 1. Characteristic water quality parameters for open well samples (March 2010)

Sr. No.	Place	Depth (m)	pH	D.O. (mg/L)	EC (μ S/cm)	TDS (mg/L)	Sulfate (mg/L)	Chloride (mg/L)	Alkalinity (mg/L)	BOD (mg/L)	Nitrate ($\text{mg NO}_3^-/\text{L}$)	Fluoride (mg/L)
1.	Kakarmatta	5.5	7.4	4.0	614	404	1.0	110	415	3.8	0.4	0.25
2.	Maduadih	9.8	7.4	5.4	822	541	13.0	115	600	2.7	0.2	0.30
3.	Lohta	14.4	7.5	5.2	912	600	29.5	95	600	2.6	27.0	1.10
4.	Mahespur	12.8	8.0	7.2	594	391	28.5	60	350	1.0	5.0	0.35
5.	Lahartara	6.0	7.7	6.7	383	252	2.0	15	320	0.4	3.2	0.65
6.	Shivpur	16.3	8.2	7.4	1070	704	215.0	155	460	1.9	130.5	0.75
7.	Bhojubeer	16.1	7.3	6.0	943	621	155.0	90	565	1.1	67.5	1.20
8.	Pandeypur	5.9	8.6	7.5	825	543	40.0	100	475	1.6	33.8	1.25
9.	Ashapur	16.0	7.6	5.5	408	269	2.5	15	375	1.1	1.1	0.50
10.	Rustumpur	9.0	7.6	5.0	515	339	7.5	20	385	0.4	10.8	0.80
11.	Chirai gaun	21.0	7.6	2.0	594	391	120.0	135	300	1.4	0.5	0.10
12.	Kamauli	20.0	7.8	1.4	746	491	15.0	80	450	0.3	22.5	0.55
13.	Paigambarpur	15.9	8.2	4.3	904	595	54.0	130	600	4.1	3.2	0.80
14.	Alaipur	2.5	8.1	1.9	977	643	13.0	103	575	5.1	0.5	0.85
15.	Chaukaghat	4.0	8.5	6.5	535	352	34.0	115	400	2.7	0.5	0.70
16.	Jagatgunj	6.5	8.1	5.3	699	460	36.0	130	425	2.6	2.3	0.45
17.	Chetgunj	5.0	7.4	5.0	428	282	30.0	55	350	2.8	3.9	0.10
18.	Beniabagh	2.5	7.3	4.9	456	300	30.5	55	325	2.7	0.5	0.15

DO = Dissolved Oxygen; EC = Electrical Conductivity, TDS = Total Dissolved Solids, BOD = Biochemical Oxygen Demand.

Table 2. Characteristic water quality parameters for tube well samples (March 2010)

Sr. No.	Place	Depth (m)	pH	D.O. (mg/L)	EC (μ S/cm)	TDS (mg/L)	Sulfate (mg/L)	Chloride (mg/L)	Alkalinity (mg/L)	BOD (mg/L)	Nitrate ($\text{mg NO}_3^-/\text{L}$)	Fluoride (mg/L)
1.	Bhelupur	200	7.9	6.2	580	348	36	53	290	0.8	5.1	0.8
2.	Beniabagh	213	7.3	6.5	619	398	35	52	285	0.7	13.5	0.7
3.	Ramkatora	213	7.3	6.7	1006	664	134	124	335	0.1	27.5	1.1
4.	Nati-imali 1	213	7.3	6.4	748	495	46	53	340	0.5	10.1	0.9
5.	Nati-imali 2	213	7.3	6.3	1050	689	122	125	320	0.4	1.8	0.8
6.	Maidagin	200	7.7	6.9	638	446	58	53	290	1.0	5.6	0.9
7.	Chowk	300	7.4	6.7	502	328	38	31	260	0.9	5.4	1.0
8.	Ratnakarpark	210	7.2	6.0	468	308	8	18	260	0.4	0.5	0.6
9.	Townhall	200	7.6	6.5	672	442	24	24	285	0.8	0.3	0.8
10.	Kotwali	213	7.1	5.9	752	495	26	31	335	1.0	1.1	Nil
11.	Machhodari	100	7.3	6.0	811	531	34	39	260	1.2	1.1	0.1
12.	Rajghat 1	200	7.1	5.8	720	475	6	21	310	0.9	1.2	Nil
13.	Rajghat 2	200	7.3	6.6	662	435	5	16	320	0.2	2.3	0.4
14.	Alaipur	210	7.1	6.6	663	436	2	9	325	0.6	0.5	0.8
15.	Chaukaghat	150	7.4	6.4	728	477	8	14	335	0.8	0.5	0.3
16.	Bhojubir	244	7.3	6.0	674	443	28	51	335	0.3	1.1	0.2
17.	Shivpur	150	7.6	6.1	989	647	4	160	310	0.4	4.5	Nil
18.	Banaras club	213	7.5	6.2	820	540	50	122	335	1.0	18.0	0.3
19.	Neel cottage	232	7.6	6.9	885	585	1	75	315	1.1	5.0	0.2
20.	Azad park	210	7.6	6.6	646	424	88	30	330	0.5	6.8	0.5
21.	Maduadih	100	8.0	6.7	580	385	3	44	295	0.8	0.5	0.2
22.	Kakarmatta	-	7.2	6.8	568	372	1	42	290	0.7	0.5	Nil
23.	BHU	-	7.2	7.0	582	382	1	47	300	0.7	0.2	Nil
24.	Bhadaini	210	8.5	7.1	335	221	30	55	210	3.6	0.5	0.8

DO = Dissolved Oxygen; EC = Electrical Conductivity, TDS = Total Dissolved Solids, BOD = Biochemical Oxygen Demand.

of the open wells of middle zone of Varanasi city show moderate level of D.O. between 4.0–6.0 mg/L.

pH :

The pH value is one of the most frequently used water quality parameters. It is measure of concentration of hydrogen ions. It is observed that all water samples, both from open wells as well as tube wells show pH between 7.0 to 8.5, which lies within permissible limits (6.5–8.5) for drinking.

Alkalinity :

Alkalinity is measure of concentration of carbonate, bicarbonate and hydroxyl ions. It changes the taste of water used for drinking purpose. Carbonates and bicarbonates are being estimated from the alkalinity values¹⁴. It is observed that alkalinity in tube wells water samples varies from 210 to 340 mg/L. Alkalinity levels more than 200 mg/L as CaCO₃ is considered permissible only in the absence of alternative source of water¹⁵. Open wells show still higher ranges from 310 to 600 mg/L of alkalinity. Beyond 200 mg/L, alkalinity imparts unpleasant taste in water, although in absence of alternate source for drinking water, the permissible limit is extended up to 600 mg/L as CaCO₃.

Total dissolve solids (TDS) :

Dissolve solids is one of the important parameter of water for drinking purpose. It should be below 500 mg/L and in absence of alternative source it may be allowed up to 2000 mg/L¹⁵. Beyond 500 mg/L of dissolved solids, the palatability of water decreases in drinking water and may cause gastro intestinal irritation. The data shows high TDS (> 500 mg/L) value in 39% samples of open wells which is situated across the Varuna river, central zone and western part. While 24% tube wells samples shows high TDS value (> 500 mg/L). These tube wells are situated in northern zone (Shivpur, Banaras club), central zone (Neel cottage, Ramkatora and Nati-imali). The map showing TDS variation in open wells and tube wells are given in Figs. 1a and 1b. The most of the open wells is not found suitable for drinking purpose owing to high TDS concentration, which is mainly due to seepage of surface water from open drains and their proximity to the industrial area or may be due to transportation sector. TDS in ground water can also be due to natural sources such as sewage, urban run-off and industrial wastes^{16,17}.

Nitrate :

Nitrate is a common ground water as well as surface

(a)

(b)

Fig. 1. (a) Map of TDS variation in open wells water samples of Varanasi, (b) in tube well water samples.

water contaminant which are causing health related problems in infants and animals, and eutrophication in surface water bodies^{18,19}. There are many pathways for the entry of nitrate to subsurface system either directly through the precipitation of nitrogen oxides, leaching from nitrous fertilizers, and ground water recharge with nitrate contaminated river water, by nitrification and in urban areas through industries²⁰⁻²². Major sources of nitrate in water are sewage and mains leakage, septic tanks, industrial spillages, contaminated land, landfills, river or channel infiltration, chemical fertilizers, house building, storm water and direct recharge etc.¹⁹. Additionally, due to human activities increase in atmospheric nitrogen compounds in Southeast Asia may be a potential source of nitrate in the surface water and ultimately goes in shallow ground water of megacity areas^{23,24}. The massive fertilizers production and its inappropriate use in agriculture throughout the world have increased the quantity of reactive nitrogen in terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems^{25,26}. Afforestation appears to be helpful to protect water quality because it reduce agricultural inputs²⁷ and by deep root extraction of nitrate stored in the soil pore water^{26,28,29}. Forest cover percentage is a good indicator of ground water nitrate levels. Large percentage of forest cover is responsible to reduce the nitrate concentrations³⁰.

European countries such as Denmark, Germany and the Netherlands have encouraged change land use from arable agriculture to woodland to reduce agricultural diffuse pollution and achieved better water quality^{31,32}. When nitrogenous fertilizers applied once in soils it converts rapidly into highly soluble and easily leachable forms of nitrate. As the quantity of nitrogen in the soil exceeds than the amount of plant's use, the excess nitrate leaches out from the root zone by water percolating through the soil profile and ultimately reaches to the ground water and responsible to cause harmful biological effects in human beings³³. However, the magnitude of leaching of nitrate to ground water depends on the characteristics of soil, types of crop grown, quantity of chemical fertilizers used, and management practices etc.³⁴.

Keshari³⁵ presented the spatial distribution of nitrate concentration in the Varanasi city area. The nitrate concentration at Kamauli, Shivpur, Bhojpur, Lohta, Shivdaspur, Kakarmatha and Bhojubar has significantly exceeded the maximum permissible limit of 45 mg NO₃⁻/L. The nitrate concentration variation in open well and tube well water samples as observed in the present study is shown in Figs. 2a and 2b. It is observed that the level of concentration reported by Keshari³⁵ is significantly higher than observed in this study.

Fig. 2. (a) Map of nitrate concentration variation in open wells water samples of Varanasi, (b) in tube well water samples.

The observations reveal that water of open well of Shivpur and Bhojubeer (northern zone of city) show nitrate concentrations more than 45 mg NO₃⁻/L (permissible limit for nitrate). Water having nitrate concentration below 22.5 mg NO₃⁻/L is said to be safe for agricultural uses, but higher than 22.5 mg NO₃⁻/L is not good for agricultural purpose³⁶. Thus, water from open wells of Pandeypur (northern zone), Lohta (western zone) and Kamauli (eastern zone) of city show nitrate concentration greater than the permissible limit for agricultural purpose. However in case of tube well, highest nitrate concentration was found 27 mg NO₃⁻/L only at Ramkatora. To control and manage the ground water quality, it is important to identify the factors affecting nitrate concentration in the ground water⁴. Land use and aquifer properties are primary factors affecting nitrate concentration in ground water^{4,37}. Lichtenberg and Shapiro³⁸ reported that hydrological conditions are important factor and responsible for nitrate contamination of ground water. Several researchers have examined and concluded that site topography may be a possible factor to influence nitrate contamination of the ground water in agricultural areas³⁹⁻⁴¹. "Methemoglobinemia" popularly known as blue baby syndrome is the most common human health problem due to high intake of nitrate. Consumption of high nitrate contaminated water may increase the risk of respiratory tract infections and goiter development in children^{42,43}. Bladder and ovarian cancer, insulin dependent diabetes mellitus and genotoxic effects at the chromosomal level are also some possible health impacts reported from high nitrate consumption through water⁴⁴. Understanding the effects of industry and agriculture on nitrate contamination in ground water is very important to encourage policy makers/planners to develop strategies to protect ground water resource from such type of contamination.

Biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) :

BOD test is an important environmental parameter which determines the relative oxygen requirements of waste waters, effluents and polluted waters. It measures the utilization of molecular oxygen for the biochemical degradation of organic materials i.e. carbonaceous demand during an incubation period as well as the quantity of oxygen used to oxidize inorganic materials such as sulfides and ferrous ions⁴⁵. The observation indicates that all tube wells are safe with respect to BOD variation. For

open wells, 44% of samples show high BOD above 2 mg/L¹⁵. In southeast Kakarmatta and northern zone (Alaipur and Paigambarpur) also there is high BOD.

Chloride :

Chloride is one among most common anions and present naturally in ground water because of its easy solubility from soil to ground water⁴⁶. High concentrations of chloride in water may be due to road salt applications or storage and septic tank leachate. In general, it is considered that chloride has no any negative impact on human health⁴⁷. However, Hutchinson⁴⁸ reported that consumption of high chloride may cause some health problems including kidney diseases. In most of the water samples of open and tube wells, the concentration of chloride is within 100 mg/L, except some places where it goes up to 200 mg/L. In India, the desirable limit for chloride in drinking water is 250 mg/L¹⁵.

Sulfate :

Sulfate occurs naturally in drinking water through the dissolution of rock minerals such as magnesium sulfate (Epsom salt), sodium sulfate (Glauber's salt), and calcium sulfate (gypsum). High levels of sulfate in drinking water may cause diarrhea in children as well as elderly peoples^{49,50}. In respect to sulfate concentration, all values are within permissible limit of 250 mg/L for drinking purpose¹⁵. High soluble sulfates with common cations calcium, magnesium and sodium can be present in high concentration in ground water⁵¹. The maximum value of sulfate is 215 mg/L in open well of Shivpur.

Fluoride :

Fluoride is another essential element for human health. Its deficiency as well as high concentrations both is harmful to humans particularly in teeth and bones. Occurrence of fluorides in soil, water, plants, animals and humans in trace quantities is due to natural activities. Several factors such as pH, total dissolved solids, alkalinity, acidity and porosity of the rocks and soil, temperature, depth of wells, etc. may affect the natural concentration of fluoride in water⁵²⁻⁵⁶. More than 65 million people including 6 million children of 199 districts in 20 states of India is suffering from fluorosis⁵⁷. The higher concentration of fluoride in Indian ground water is likely to be associated with igneous and metamorphic rocks⁵⁸. WHO⁵⁹ has been given 1.5 mg/L fluoride as a maximum guideline value

for fluoride in drinking water. In India, BIS¹⁵ has prescribed the standard for fluoride concentration in drinking water 1.0 mg/L as desirable and 1.5 mg/L as permissible limit. Presence of high fluoride concentration in ground water causing fluorosis and it has become one of the most important geo-environmental issues related with human health in many countries of the world including India⁶⁰.

Among 18 open wells (Fig. 3a) sites of Varanasi city, only Lohta, Bhojubeer and Pandeypur is found under safe limit for fluoride concentration in water which has been prescribed by BIS. Rest 15 sites are under threat condition of developing teeth and bone related health problems. Similarly, in case of tube wells (Fig. 3b) only Ramkatora and Chowk were found safe as per the limit of BIS, whereas fluoride concentration was not detected at five locations namely Kotwali, Rajghatl, Shivpur,

characteristics and agricultural activities in an intensively cultivated district. A great proportion of ground water suffers from both the problems nitrate and fluoride of contamination. An increase in fluoride concentration in ground water is the resultant of some major human activities like application of phosphatic fertilizers, pesticides and sewage and sludges, depletion of ground water table etc.⁶². The fluoride concentration in ground water depends on the use of the quantity of single super phosphate fertilizers because this type of fertilizers is made by using fluoride and phosphate containing rocks⁶³. A significant positive relationship between consumption of fluoride contaminated water and the appearance of dental fluorosis has been reported by several researchers⁶⁴⁻⁶⁶. China, India and Africa are reported to have high fluoride levels in water⁶⁷⁻⁷¹. In biomaterials, urine and blood has been proposed as the most reliable indicator for the exposure of daily level of fluoride in human beings⁷².

Fig. 3. (a) Map of fluoride concentration variation in open wells water samples of Varanasi, (b) in tube well water samples.

Kakarmatta and BHU and the water of these locations not appears good for drinking purpose. Concentration of fluoride in between 0.5–1.0 mg/L has considered beneficial to human, especially for the maintenance of healthy teeth and bones^{60,61}, while >1.5 mg/L fluoride consumption may cause dental and skeletal fluorosis. Kundu *et al.*⁶⁰ inferred that in India, nitrate and fluoride contamination in ground water is due to the function of lithology, soil

Indian standard and WHO guideline values for water quality parameters for drinking purpose :

Table 3 contains desirable limits of common water quality parameters as per Indian standard¹⁵ and WHO guideline values⁵⁹ for drinking purpose. Indian standard provides desirable as well as permissible limit (in absence of alternate options) of water quality parameters for drinking purpose.

Table 3. Indian standard and WHO guideline value for drinking water

Parameter (mg/L)	Indian standard ¹⁵	WHO guideline value ⁵⁹
pH	6.5–8.5	–
TDS	500	–
Sulfate (as SO ₄ ²⁻)	200	500
Chloride (as Cl ⁻)	250	250
Alkalinity (as CaCO ₃)	200	–
Nitrate (as NO ₃ ⁻)	45	50
Fluoride	1.0–1.5	1.5

The pH values of all the tested water samples were found to be within the range of Indian standard for drinking purpose. The observed value of alkalinity ranged from 210 to 340 mg/L in tube wells and 310 to 600 mg/L in open wells, all of them being higher than the desirable limit for alkalinity in drinking water as per Indian standards. Higher alkalinity levels cause unpleasant taste in water¹⁵. In terms of TDS, around 39% samples of open wells and 24% of tube wells exceeded the desirable limit of 500 mg/L. Higher levels of TDS in drinking water may cause gastro intestinal irritation in human. TDS values ranged between 252 to 643 mg/L in open wells and 221 to 689 mg/L in tube wells. High TDS values in open wells are likely to be due to the surface run-off from open drains. The nitrate concentration in open well samples ranged from 0.2 to 167 mg NO₃⁻/L, and in tube wells from 0.2 to 27.5 mg NO₃⁻/L. Open wells water samples of Shivpur and Bhojubeer area are found to be high in nitrate, and not suitable for drinking purpose. Among major possible sources of nitrate in ground water¹⁹, leakage of untreated sewage to well system appears the cause of high nitrate in Varanasi. The observed values of chloride ranged from 15–155 mg/L in open wells and 9–160 mg/L in tube wells, which are all within permissible limit (250 mg/L) for drinking. The sulfate concentration in the water samples ranged from 1–215 mg/L in open wells and 1–134 mg/L in tube wells. Thus, both open wells and tube well sources are found safe for drinking purpose with respect to sulfate concentration¹⁵, except open wells from Shivpur area where the sulfate concentration exceeded 200 mg/L. High sulfate levels in drinking water has laxative effect on public health, children as well as elderly people may be affected with diarrhea due to high sulfate concentration in ground water⁵⁰. The fluoride concentrations were found in the range of 0.10–1.25 mg/L

from open wells and 0.1–1.1 mg/L in tube wells. Most of the water samples either open wells or tube wells are having below 1.0 mg/L fluoride level, which needs to add the fluoride in water to attain the desirable limit for drinking purpose. Because, below 1.0 mg/L of fluoride in drinking water may damage the health of teeth⁶⁰. Only around 17% of samples from open wells and 8% from tube wells showed fluoride concentration in 1.0–1.5 mg/L range, which is considered safe for drinking purpose. Some 83% of open well samples and 92% of tube well samples were found to have fluoride concentration less than 1.0 mg/L, which is considered desirable lower limit for drinking¹⁵.

Arsenic in the water samples around Varanasi :

Ali Shah⁷³ reported the concentration of arsenic in tube well water samples of middle Ganga plain (around Varanasi city), Uttar Pradesh, ranged from 3–6 µg/L, which is found safe and within permissible limit prescribed by WHO (10 µg/L)⁵⁹ as well as BIS (50 µg/L)¹⁵.

Raju⁷⁴ estimated arsenic concentration in tube well water samples around the Varanasi city. Arsenic concentrations were checked in 68 locations and the concentration varied in the range of 3–80 µg/L. Among which, 14% of the samples were found to have more than 10 µg/L and 5% of the samples were exceeded 50 µg/L. Author found that some villages such as Bahadurpur, Bhakhara, Bhojpur, Jalilpur, Kateswar, Kodupur, Madhiya, Ratanpur and Semra were having high arsenic concentrations. Thus, around 81% tube well water samples of total studied area were found safe with respect to arsenic drinking purpose Varanasi area.

Conclusion

A press release of UNO Secretary General on World Water Day (2002) “An estimated 1.1 billion people do not have safe drinking water, 2.5 billion people has not avail drinking water in proper sanitation. More than 5 million people are dying every year from water related diseases; it is 10 times more the number of persons killed in wars, on average, each year. This statistics proves the importance of availability of high quality drinking water throughout world. Even where supplies are good enough or plentiful, they are also increasing towards the risk due to the pollution and rising demand. Two thirds of the world’s population will be in the compulsion of survival

and may live in countries where already shortage of water either moderate or severe by the year 2025”⁵. As everyone knows water is a vital element for life and only 3% of total water present on earth is fresh water. Interestingly, only 0.01% of the total fresh water is available for the use of human⁷⁵. In this regard, the objective of the present study was to examine the quality of different water sources for drinking purpose. Within the limits of experimental procedures and analysis, 25 tube wells and 18 open wells were selected from across the city area of Varanasi. It is observed that most of tube wells are safe for drinking purpose, with respect to pH, TDS, alkalinity, chloride, sulfate, nitrate, DO and BOD. The TDS concentration of some tube wells is found more than the desirable limit, but within permissible limit for drinking purpose. Alkalinity of all the tube wells water exceeded the desirable limit of 200 mg/L, but is within permissible limit of 600 mg/L for drinking. Most of the open wells draw water from more than 10 m depth. They have less dissolve oxygen and higher biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) than desirable limits (>6 mg/L, and <2 mg/L respectively) for drinking purpose. Open wells of Shivpur, Bhojubeer, Pandeypur (in northern zone), Alaipur (in central zone) and Lohta and Maduadiha (in western zone) of the city have high concentration of TDS and alkalinity ranging between 500–750 mg/L and 400–600 mg/L respectively. Open wells of Shivpur and Bhojubir in northern zone show nitrate concentrations of 130.5 and 67.5 mg NO_3^-/L respectively, which is beyond permissible limit for drinking purpose. Open wells of Pandeypur in northern zone, Lohta in western zone and Kamauli in eastern zone show nitrate concentrations of 33.8, 27.0 and 22.5 mg NO_3^-/L respectively. In case of fluoride it has been observed that mostly low concentration present than the desirable limit and water may affect the teeth and bones of the population which depend for drinking in that areas. Although these concentrations are within permissible limit for drinking, these areas need to be kept under monitoring program for nitrate. All areas which are showing high concentration of nitrate, dissolve solids and alkalinity should be kept in risk zone and need continuous monitoring. Issues of adverse impact of these parameters on crops, animals and ecosystem may be looked into in detail.

Experimental

Study area :

Varanasi is located in southwest portion of Uttar Pradesh (India) and having the geographical coordinates as $82^\circ 15'$ to $83^\circ 30'$ East longitude and $24^\circ 35'$ to $25^\circ 30'$ North latitude. The geographical area of the district is 1535 km^2 . Varanasi district forms part of central Ganga plain and physiographically the district can be divided into two physical regions, i.e. the northern alluvial plain and the southern plateau area. The northern alluvial plain is drained by the Ganga and its tributaries namely the *Gomti* and *Varuna* rivers. The southern plateau comprising of extensive hillocks and mesas of *Vindhyan* sandstone and shales, is deeply dissected by the *Karamnasa* river and its effluents. The total population of Varanasi district is 31.4 lakh having urban population 12.6 lakh and rural population about 18.8 lakh as per the census 2001. The Varanasi district falls in the subtropical region and its climate is classified as tropical to subtropical type, characterized by hot summer and severe winter. The greater part of district receives the annual rainfall through south west monsoon between July and September. The average normal rainfall of the city is 1113.4 mm⁷⁶.

Data used :

Locations of different ground water samples are obtained using Global Positioning System. The various ground water quality parameters like pH, total dissolve solids (TDS), dissolve oxygen, biochemical oxygen demand, chloride, alkalinity, sulfate, nitrate and fluoride were examined as per standard methods. Nitrate and fluoride were determined by using Ion Selective Electrode method as per Standard Methods⁷⁷.

Software used :

ArcGIS8.1 software has been developed by ESRI Inc. is one of the leading software for desktop GIS and mapping. ArcGIS gives the power to visualize, explore, query, and analyze data geographically. In this study ArcGIS is used for display of raster data, digitizing different features and querying the data geographically and for finding the attributes of any features on map. ArcGIS's spatial analyst is a tool which helps us to do analysis and understand spatial relationships in our data. Spatial analyst has been used for generation of various water quality maps.

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